

Moc dysypowana w regulatorze liniowych ETH

Using Internal LDO with External MOSFET (Default Configuration)

Using an LDO or external MOSFET does imply a low efficiency and then high power dissipation. Equation 1 illustrates power dissipation for an LDO.

$$P_{\text{LOSSES(MAX)}} = (V_{\text{AVDDH(MAX)}} - V_{\text{DVDDL(MIN)}}) \times I_{\text{DVDDL+AVDDL(MAX)}}$$

$$P_{\text{LOSSES(MAX)}} = 0.62\text{W}$$

Eq. 1

The P-Channel MOSFET must dissipate 100% of this power. The maximum ambient temperature achievable, assuming the worst-case scenario, is noted in Equation 2.

$$T_{\text{AMBIENT(MAX)}} = T_{\text{JUNCTION(MAX)}} - (R\theta_{\text{JA}} \times P_{\text{LOSSES(MAX)}})$$

Eq. 2

Figure 5. Maximum Ambient Temperature vs. MOSFET Thermal Resistance

A06604 rezystancja termiczna

Thermal Characteristics					
Parameter		Symbol	Typ	Max	Units
Maximum Junction-to-Ambient ^A	t ≤ 10s	R _{θJA}	78	110	°C/W
Maximum Junction-to-Ambient ^{A,D}	Steady-State		106	150	°C/W
Maximum Junction-to-Lead	Steady-State	R _{θJL}	64	80	°C/W

Zakładam najniższą ze względu że pracuje tylko 1 tranzystor a drugi ma wszystkie nóżki umasowione powodując odprowadzanie ciepła z krzemu. Tranzystor będzie umieszczony na placku miedzi działającej jak radiator

Figure 2. KSZ9031 Internal LDO Controller Driving External MOSFET

Table 2. KSZ9031MNX (GMII) Worst Case Power Consumption in 1000Base-T Mode

Rail	Typical Consumption (mA)	Typical +20% (Process Variation) (mA)
Analog TX/RX Interface (AVDDH @ 3.3V)	68	82
Digital Interface and I/Os (DVDDH @ 3.3V)	54	65
Analog/Digital Core and PLL (DVDDL, AVDDL, AVDDL_PLL @ 1.2V)	221	265

- P-channel
- 500 mA (continuous current)
- 3.3V or 2.5V (source – input voltage)
- 1.2V (drain – output voltage)
- V_{GS} in the range of:
 - (-1.2V to -1.5V) @ 500 mA for 3.3V source voltage
 - (-1.0V to -1.1V) @ 500 mA for 2.5V source voltage

P-Channel: TYPICAL ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS

Fig 1: On-Region Characteristics (Note E)

Figure 2: Transfer Characteristics (Note E)